

Analysis of the HTR-10 benchmark using TRIPOLI-5

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ABSTRACT

TRIPOLI-5[®] is the next-generation Monte Carlo particle-transport code currently under co-development at CEA and ASNR, France. In order to model High-Temperature Reactors (HTRs) of the pebble-bed or prismatic type, TRIPOLI-5 relies on CASTOR (Constructor and Analyzer of STOchastic Realizations), a Monte Carlo sampler of stochastic geometries developed at CEA. In this work, we provide an overview of the features recently implemented in CASTOR, including the Jodrey-Tory (JT) algorithm and the possibility of using a sphere packing generated with Discrete Element Method (DEM) software, in view of addressing configurations with high packing fractions. An application to the simulation of the HTR-10 pebble-bed reactor benchmark is discussed, and the results obtained with TRIPOLI-5 (using both the JT algorithm and DEM geometries) are compared to those of OpenMC (using the JT algorithm).

Keywords: HTR, TRIPOLI-5, spherical inclusions, pebble-bed, CASTOR

1. INTRODUCTION

High-Temperature Reactors (HTRs) of the prismatic or pebble-bed type offer many advantages in terms of enhanced safety, flexibility and efficiency, and for these reasons have been selected as one of the six Gen-IV nuclear system candidates. Several HTRs demonstrators have been built in recent years, such as the HTR-10 and HTR-PM in China, and many others are being designed in France and in the USA.

The fuel of HTRs has a peculiar double-heterogeneity structure, typically resulting from TRi-structural ISOtropic (TRISO) fuel particles randomly dispersed within either graphite compact matrices organized in a hexagonal lattice (in the prismatic design) or within graphite pebbles themselves randomly dispersed within the core, intermixed with pure graphite pebbles (in the pebble-bed design).

Over the last decade, intensive efforts have been devoted to the development of simulation tools capable of accurately modeling radiation transport within HTRs, encompassing fuel depletion and multi-physics feedback [1–7]. While in the earlier works deterministic solvers were largely used [8], thanks to the increased available computer power and the improvements in the simulation algorithms the focus is progressively shifting towards Monte Carlo codes, which naturally allow for a high-fidelity description of HTRs geometries including billions of randomly dispersed TRISO particles.

In this context, the HTR-10, a 10 MWt prototype high-temperature pebble-bed reactor operated at the Tsinghua University (China) is attracting broad interest in that its specifications and key neutronic parameters have been transformed into an international benchmark [8,9], particularly well suited for the validation of simulation codes. At CEA, pioneering work on the modeling of the HTR-10 has been carried out using the deterministic solver APOLLO2 and the Monte Carlo code TRIPOLI-4[®] in 2004 [10], with several simplifying assumptions concerning the geometry of the pebbles.

More recently, a specialized Monte Carlo sampler called CASTOR (Constructor and Analyzer of STOchastic Realizations) has been developed at CEA, covering both spherical inclusions and Markov media [11].

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In its earlier version, CASTOR relied on a mesh-based improved version of the Random Sequential Addition (RSA) algorithm to sample random spherical inclusions, which is known to achieve a maximum packing fraction of about $\xi \sim 0.38$ [11]. RSA is thus adequate for the relatively low packing fraction of the TRISOs within a pebble, but fails for the considerably higher packing fractions typical of pebble beds within HTRs.

In this work, first we provide an overview of the novel features implemented in CASTOR in order to overcome this limitation, including the Jodrey-Tory (JT) algorithm [12] and the possibility of using a sphere packing generated with Discrete Element Method (DEM) software [13]. Then, we illustrate these capabilities by revisiting the HTR-10 benchmark: simulations will be carried out with TRIPOLI-5[®] [14], the next-generation Monte Carlo particle-transport code currently under co-development at CEA and ASNR, using the configurations sampled with CASTOR. The results obtained with TRIPOLI-5 (with both the JT algorithm and DEM geometries) are compared to those of OpenMC [15], which relies on the Close Random Packing (CRP) scheme, also based on the JT algorithm.

2. NEW FEATURES IN CASTOR FOR SPHERICAL INCLUSIONS

CASTOR now benefits from two features specifically developed to sample random spherical inclusion models with packing fractions around $\xi \sim 0.6$, which is the typical value for pebble beds in HTRs.

The principle of RSA is to sample the centers of the spheres sequentially: a trial center is rejected if the corresponding sphere has some overlapping with previously positioned spheres [11]. The legacy mesh-accelerated RSA method is applied in CASTOR whenever the packing fraction is lower than a user-defined threshold (set to $\xi \sim 0.37$ by default), which ensures satisfactory computational efficiency. For higher packing fractions, CASTOR has been endowed with the JT algorithm: spheres are assigned an inner and an outer diameter, whose values are iteratively adjusted. The inner diameter corresponds to the true minimum center-to-center distance between the spheres, whereas the outer diameter is used to search and progressively remove the overlaps between the packed spheres: at each iteration, the worst overlap is suppressed by separating the spheres along the diameter. The JT algorithm converges when the outer diameter shrinks towards the inner diameter, or when the target packing fraction is achieved. A tolerance is set on the contraction rate, to prevent numerical instabilities. For a thorough discussion, see Ref. 12. This method allows easily attaining packing fractions slightly above $\xi \sim 0.64$, which covers the needs of HTRs models. The JT algorithm is also implemented in OpenMC, under the name of CRP method [15]. The implementation of the JT algorithm in CASTOR has been extensively verified against the existing CRP method of OpenMC; its performance has been also carefully assessed and deemed satisfactory: results will be presented in a forthcoming extended work.

In addition to the JT algorithm, CASTOR can now import a sphere packing generated from an external DEM code, under the form of a collection of sphere centers with given radii. DEM codes are customarily used in the modeling of pebble-bed configurations [1–5, 9], since they can numerically simulate the dynamics of the pebbles (treated as granular media) from their insertion into the core to their final resting position, taking explicitly into account the forces exerted between the media and between the media and the walls of the container [13]. Although the interface of CASTOR is flexible and can in principle be adapted to arbitrary formats, for this work we have coupled CASTOR with the DEM code LIGGGHTS (LAMMPS Improved for General Granular and Granular Heat Transfer Simulations), an open-source software capable of efficiently simulating the realistic dynamics of granular media, based on the classical molecular dynamics simulator LAMMPS [13, 16]. LIGGGHTS version 3 includes several models for granular media interactions, handles account complex geometrical shapes for the containers, and can be easily parallelized using the MPI paradigm [16].

Once the sphere packing has been sampled using the JT (or RSA) algorithm or imported from the DEM code, CASTOR handles the creation of inner spherical shells, if needed, and the ‘coloring’ procedure (assigning material compositions to each sphere, with position-dependent probabilities, if required).

For fuel pebbles, CASTOR additionally samples the positions of the TRISO particles, typically using the Fast RSA algorithm due to the low packing fraction, and for each sampled position of the TRISO particles it determines the multi-shell structure of the fuel kernel and graphite layers. For the optimization of the generated geometries, we set a user-defined mesh that improves the performance of the construction step and accelerates the nearest-neighbor search during particle transport.

The configurations sampled with CASTOR can be finally exported in the geometry format used by either TRIPOLI-4 or TRIPOLI-5. For TRIPOLI-5, we rely on the geometry navigation engine AGORA, whose modeling capabilities have been designed with a multi-nested description, based on the Constructive Solid Geometry (CSG) paradigm [17].

3. ANALYSIS OF THE HTR-10 BENCHMARK

We describe now the preliminary analysis of the HTR-10 benchmark using TRIPOLI-5 (coupled with CASTOR) and OpenMC. The models of HTR-10 have been developed from scratch for this work, following the detailed specifications of the initial critical core provided in Ref. 9. For the first divergence, the core consisted of a random arrangement of 16890 mixed pebbles: 9627 fuel pebbles, each containing an average of 8335 TRISO particles, and 7263 graphite pebbles. All simulations have been run with 100 inactive cycles, 1000 active cycles and 100000 neutrons per cycle, using the ENDF/B-VIII.0 nuclear data library [18], except otherwise stated. For each tested configuration, the simulation results discussed in the following have been systematically averaged over 5 independent random replicas: the reported uncertainty stems from both the statistical convergence of Monte Carlo (which was systematically below 15 pcm) and the dispersion due to the stochastic nature of the configurations. For the sake of simplicity, the random TRISO configuration within the fuel pebbles is chosen to be the same for all pebbles, which is known to have a negligible impact on the estimated multiplication factor [9].

3.1. Simplified Sphere Packing Geometry Using the JT Algorithm

We begin by considering the simplified HTR-10 core geometry corresponding to the 'equivalent critical height' approximation [9]. A portion of height 123.06 cm of the cylindrical core above the discharge 'conus' is filled with 16890 pebbles, which ensures a packing fraction of $\zeta = 0.61$ and is supposed to yield a reactivity consistent with that obtained using a higher-fidelity DEM code to generate the pebble configuration in the core. We have built independent models for TRIPOLI-5 and OpenMC: for each, the required pebble mixture configuration is sampled using the JT algorithm (relying on CASTOR for TRIPOLI-5, and on the internal CRP method for OpenMC). Once the geometry is sampled, the random coloring is carried out by respecting the exact number of pebbles of each kind, and the number of TRISO particles is kept fixed to 8335. For illustration, two configurations of the TRIPOLI-5 and OpenMC models are shown in Fig. 1. The lower portion of the core in the conus and in the discharge channel is filled with homogenized graphite, whose specifications are taken from Ref. 9.

For the reference configuration with $\zeta = 0.61$, the average multiplication factor computed with TRIPOLI-5 is $k_{eff} = 1.00204 \pm 0.00017$. The small offset with respect to criticality (which is coherent with typical values found for other criticality benchmarks) can be attributed to the technological uncertainties and to the impact of the nuclear data library. The corresponding OpenMC model gives $k_{eff} = 1.00190 \pm 0.00015$, which is entirely consistent with the result of the TRIPOLI-5 model. This finding is complemented by the analysis of the fundamental mode, which is shown in Fig. 2: an excellent agreement is found. In order to probe the effect of nuclear data, we have run a separate series of replicas for the reference configuration using the JEFF-3.3 library [19], which yields $k_{eff} = 1.00123 \pm 0.00017$.

We have singled out the effect of the random coloring procedure with respect to the effect of the random positioning of the spheres by selecting a given realization sampled with the JT algorithm and resampling the pebble types (keeping their respective number fixed). The multiplication factor of the original configuration (with $\zeta = 0.61$) reads $k_{eff} = 1.00140 \pm 0.00013$, and the average over 5 replicas

Figure 1. HTR-10 benchmark models based on the simplified cylindrical core with equivalent height. The core is filled with 16890 pebbles sampled using the JT algorithm. Left: zoom on the fuel and graphite pebbles (top) and on the TRISO particles within the fuel pebbles (bottom); center: the TRIPOLI-5 model; right: the OpenMC model.

Figure 2. The average fundamental neutron flux corresponding to the reference HTR-10 configuration ($\xi = 0.61$) using the JT model. Left: TRIPOLI-5 (blue) and OpenMC (red); right: the corresponding Student t -test.

with randomized colors gives $k_{eff} = 1.00158 \pm 0.00031$.

The effect of the packing fraction has been then quantified by adjusting the equivalent height of the core while keeping the number of fuel and graphite pebbles fixed. A packing fraction $\xi = 0.62$ is achieved by setting the equivalent height to 121.075 cm, which yields $k_{eff} = 1.00561 \pm 0.00015$. Conversely, a packing fraction $\xi = 0.60$ is achieved by setting the equivalent height to 125.111 cm, which yields $k_{eff} = 0.99758 \pm 0.00014$. The effect of the packing fraction is thus much larger than the one of coloring.

Finally, we have assessed the impact of the number of TRISO particles in the fuel pebbles. Increasing their packing fraction from 0.05025 (8335 particles) to 0.05125 (8501 particles) yields $k_{eff} = 1.00580 \pm$

0.00017. Conversely, decreasing their packing fraction to 0.04925 (8169 particles) yields $k_{eff} = 0.99806 \pm 0.00013$. The average reactivity worth of each TRISO particle is thus about 1.4×10^{-4} pcm.

3.2. Realistic Sphere Packing Geometry Using the LIGGGHTS Code

We then consider the realistic HTR-10 geometry obtained by using LIGGGHTS to sample the pebbled dynamics from insertion to settling into the core, and exporting the resulting configurations to CASTOR. For illustration, snapshots of the pebbles falling into the core and a full reactor model for TRIPOLI-5 are shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Left: filling of the HTR-10 core using LIGGGHTS, when 3200 pebbles have been poured in the container. Center: same, after reaching the target 16890 pebbles. Right: the corresponding TRIPOLI-5 model for the critical core loading, after the pebbles have been randomly colored with CASTOR.

In LIGGGHTS, the container within which the pebbles fall includes the lower discharge cylinder, the conus and the upper core cylinder. The container geometry has been generated using the SALOME meshing tool [20]. Reflecting boundary conditions have been applied to the walls of the container. Pebbles are poured into the container from a single opening located on the top of the core vault (see Fig. 3), until exactly 16890 spheres are within the core (i.e. their centers lie above the bottom of the core cylinder). The integration time for the particle dynamics has been set to $80 \mu\text{s}$, based on the analysis of the convergence patterns. The slight density difference between fuel and graphite pebbles is neglected. The DEM simulation stops when the particle energy falls below 10^{-8} , relative to the initial energy. Literature findings show that the sphere packing generated by DEM codes is rather sensitive to the choice of the physical parameters that govern the granular media dynamics, in particular to the friction coefficients between spheres [9], and we thus expect the corresponding multiplication factor to be also dependent on this choice. Cross-referencing the settings proposed by various authors [1–5, 9], for the reference pebble configuration sampled with LIGGGHTS we have chosen the parameters provided in Tab. I. With these parameters, the average packing fraction of the generated configurations is about $\zeta = 0.606$, as estimated by CASTOR: this value is consistent with the one of the ‘equivalent height’ model filled using the JT algorithm in Sec. 3.1.

After the sphere packing has been generated by LIGGGHTS and imported in CASTOR, the spheres undergo the coloring procedure. Contrary to the case of the simplified core geometry considered in

Table I. Physical parameters for the reference pebble configuration generated with LIGGGHTS.

Parameter	Value
Pebble radius	3 cm
Pebble density	1850 kg/m ³
Young's modulus of the pebbles	10 ⁹ Pa
Young's modulus of the wall	10 ¹⁰ Pa
Poisson's ratio of the pebbles	0.2
Poisson's ratio of the wall	0.3
Pebble-pebble restitution coefficient	0.9
Pebble-wall restitution coefficient	0.3
Pebble-pebble friction coefficient	0.2
Pebble-wall friction coefficient	0.2

the previous section, here the coloring probability depends on the height of the centers of the pebbles: below the bottom of the cylindrical core, the pebbles are all of the graphite type, whereas within the cylindrical core a mixture must be sampled, respecting the target number for both pebble types.

Before examining the behavior of the TRIPOLI-5 simulations, we have probed the 'angle of repose' θ formed between the horizontal plane and the cone created by the falling pebbles on the upper surface of the core. The average value computed by CASTOR over 5 random replicas produced by LIGGGHTS is $\theta = (18.5 \pm 0.5)^\circ$, which is consistent with previous findings [9].

The average multiplication factor obtained with TRIPOLI-5 for the reference HTR-10 configuration is $k_{eff} = 1.00278 \pm 0.00022$, which is rather close to the value obtained in Sec. 3.1 for the simplified core geometry generated with the JT algorithm. The corresponding average fundamental mode is displayed in Fig. 4 and contrasted to the one computed using the JT algorithm. The two random sphere packing models have distinct chord length distributions, which are expected to subtle discrepancies (the results for the HTR-10 benchmark are nonetheless relatively close). Furthermore, we have run a separate series of replicas for the reference configuration using the JEFF-3.3 library [19] to evaluate the impact of nuclear data, which yields $k_{eff} = 1.00195 \pm 0.00026$. The effect of nuclear data is similar to the one found for the simplified core model in Sec. 3.1.

Figure 4. The average fundamental neutron flux corresponding to the reference configuration of HTR-10, computed with TRIPOLI-5. Left: sphere packing generated using LIGGGHTS (blue) or using the JT algorithm (red); right: the corresponding Student t-test.

The effect of friction, which is known to be one of the most influential parameters on the DEM dynamics for pebbles with respect to the resulting packing fraction [9], has been quantified by slightly increasing the pebble-pebble friction coefficient to 0.3 (still within the range of ‘reasonable’ values proposed in the literature). Correspondingly, the obtained average packing fraction decreases to $\xi = 0.598$ and the average multiplication factor also appreciably decreases to $k_{eff} = 1.00017 \pm 0.00017$. The effect of the pebble-wall friction has been also estimated by increasing again the pebble-wall friction coefficient to 0.3: the corresponding average multiplication factor is $k_{eff} = 1.00270 \pm 0.00017$, which shows minimal deviations with respect to the reference value.

In order to single out the effect of random coloring procedure with respect to the effect of the DEM positioning of the spheres, we have selected a given realization of the reference configuration, corresponding to $k_{eff} = 1.00232 \pm 0.00013$, and we have resampled the pebble colors (keeping again their respective number fixed): the resulting average multiplication factor is $k_{eff} = 1.00187 \pm 0.00021$. The reactivity worth of single pebbles has been assessed by pouring ten more and ten less (mixed) pebbles than the target value 16890. In the former case, we obtain $k_{eff} = 1.00304 \pm 0.00024$, whereas in the latter we obtain $k_{eff} = 1.00259 \pm 0.00017$. The average reactivity worth of a pebble is thus compatible with 2 pcm, although better statistics would be needed. Finally, the impact of the number of TRISO particles in fuel pebbles has been again estimated by increasing and decreasing their packing fraction by the same amount as in the previous section. An increase in the number of TRISO particles yields $k_{eff} = 1.00654 \pm 0.00023$, and conversely a decrease leads to $k_{eff} = 0.99889 \pm 0.00025$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work we have presented the preliminary results concerning the analysis of the HTR-10 pebble-bed reactor benchmark using TRIPOLI-5, the next-generation Monte Carlo code under development at CEA and ASNR. For the sampling of the sphere packing, new features have been implemented in CASTOR, the spherical inclusions sampler developed at CEA: the Jodrey-Tory algorithm and a coupling with the DEM code LIGGGHTS. Both strategies have been successfully tested and compared to each other and to OpenMC results. Future work will concern a more detailed analysis of the differences between the sphere packing generated by the JT algorithm or by the DEM codes: we will investigate in particular the chord length distribution within these geometries and its impact on the particle-transport properties [11]. Also, the effect on reactivity due to the choice of the physics of granular media will be assessed by coupling CASTOR with other DEM codes, such as ExaDEM, a HPC software solution built on the ExaNBody platform [21]. Finally, the impact of using delta-tracking instead of surface-tracking for particle transport in random geometries will be assessed.

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TRIPOLI-4[®] and TRIPOLI-5[®] are registered trademarks of CEA. The authors thank EDF and ASNR for partial financial support.

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